

Supporting Information

Proton migration-modulated n-doped poly(benzodifurandione) (n-PBDF) organic electrochemical transistors used for neuromorphic computing applications

Ignacio Sanjuán,^{a,} David Franco,^a Qun-Gao Chen,^b Chu-Chen Chueh,^c Wen-Ya Lee,^b
Antonio Guerrero^{a,*}*

^a Ignacio Sanjuán, David Franco, Antonio Guerrero

Institute of Advanced Materials (INAM), Universitat Jaume I, 12006 Castelló, Spain.

*E-mail corresponding authors: isanjuan@uji.es, aguerrer@uji.es

^b Qun-Gao Chen, Wen-Ya Lee

Department of Chemical Engineering and Biotechnology, National Taipei University of Technology, Taipei 106344, Taiwan.

^c Chu-Chen Chueh

Department of Chemical Engineering, National Taiwan University, Taipei 10617, Taiwan.

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H¹-NMR Spectra of monomer and n-PBDF

The H¹-NMR of the pure monomer is described (**Fig. S1a**). The peaks at 7.25 and 3.96 ppm correspond to the aromatic hydrogen and the methylene hydrogen, respectively. The synthesis of the monomer is described in the main text and the product is pure at >99 % by H¹-NMR with DMSO-d₆ and residual water as the only other signals observed. **Fig. S1b** shows the magnified H¹-NMR spectrum of the polymer. As reported previously, the signals of the polymer are not observed using this analytical technique due to the doping of the polymer. At high magnifications it is possible to observe residual signals and exchange signals of H⁺ with the residual water. The complete monomer conversion is justified by the disappearance of the BDF peaks in the n-PBDF spectrum.

Figure S1. NMR spectra of the monomer BDF (top) and the as prepared polymer n-PBDF (bottom) in DMSO-d₆.

Electrical conductivity measurements of n-PBDF

A typical 4-probe set up is used to measure the conductivity and the results are corroborated by using impedance spectroscopy.

Figure S2. Electrical conductivity measurements of the n-PBDF film. a) Scheme illustrating the principle of the 4-probe method used for the electrical conductivity measurement and the equations. b) Representative I-V voltammetry plot used for the measurement of the conductance. c) Representative Nyquist Plot used for the analysis of the film impedance.

Cyclic voltammetry stability measurements using NaCl and NaPF₆

Figure S3. Consecutive cycles of output curves registered in different electrolytes with the n-PBDF OECTs. Each cycle includes 5 output curves with different V_{gs} (0.5, 0.25, 0, -0.25, 0.5 V) but only 2 are shown. V_{ds} is cycled between 0 and 1.5 V. a) and b) 1st and 10th cycle of output curves measured in 0.1 M NaCl. c) and d) 1st and 10th cycles of output curves measured in 0.1 M NaPF₆.

Transconductance plot of devices fabricated with n-PBDF

Figure S4. Transfer curve (red) and transconductance (g_m) versus V_{gs} plot for the n-PBDF OEET in 0.1 M NaPF₆ ($V_{ds} = 1.2$, scan rate 30 mV s $^{-1}$).

Synaptic characterization of devices fabricated with n-PBDF

Figure S5. Plot of I_{ds} versus time during the application of a 10-second V_{gs} pulse and 40 s of rest time. Pulses with different V_{gs} between 0.8 and -0.5 V are applied. V_{ds} is held at 1.2 V. The measurements were stopped when the I_{ds} reached a steady value.

Figure S6. Plot of I_{ds} as a function of time during the application of paired V_{gs} pulses with varying interval times (Δt , the time between pulses). V_{gs} is 0.8 V during each pulse ($t_{\text{pulse}} = 200$ ms) and 0 V at the rest time. V_{ds} is held at 1.2 V. The black dashed line indicates the I_{ds} level of the first pulses.

Figure S7. I_{ds} current-time response under a gate voltage V_{gs} pulse [-0.5 V, 20 s] for the n-PBDF OECTs with different electrolytes.

Figure S8. Analysis of the long-term potentiation (LTP) and depression (LTD) behavior of the n-PBDF OECTs upon the application of different gate voltage pulses (V_{gs}). a) Scheme of the experimental program describing the application of sequences of gate voltage pulses for potentiation and depression. b-d) Plot of drain-source current (I_{ds}) versus time registered under the application of the LTP/LTD gate voltage sequences with different $V_{gs}(\text{set}) = 0.5, 0.8,$ and 1 V, respectively. e-g) LTP/LTD cycles of excitatory post-synaptic currents (EPSC) with the pulse number applied, derived from the data of (b-d).

Figure S9. Long-term potentiation (LTP) and depression (LTD) curve obtained for a n-PBDF OECT device with different V_{gs} (reset) voltages for depression and maintaining the same values for the rest of operating parameters, as described in the legend.

Figure S9 reveals that slightly negative V_{gs} are optimal for the LTP/LTD behavior when $V_{gs}(\text{set}) = 0.8 \text{ V}$ since the use of more negative V_{gs} leads to a device conductance level that is lower than the initial state of the device before potentiation.

Figure S10. Analysis of the long-term potentiation (LTP) and depression (LTD) behavior of the n-PBDF OECTs with longer pulse width (500 ms) and lower number of pulses. a) Scheme of the experimental program describing the application of sequences of gate voltage pulses for potentiation and depression. b) Plot of drain-source current (I_{ds}) versus time registered under the application of the LTP/LTD gate voltage sequences with $V_{gs}(set) = 0.8$ V. c) LTP/LTD cycles of excitatory post-synaptic currents (EPSC) with the pulse number applied, derived from the data of (b).

Figure S11. Plot of drain-source current (I_{ds}) versus time registered under the application of 500 ms-long LTP/LTD gate voltage sequences. 30 pulses for potentiation (LTP) and 30 pulses for depression (LTD).

Figure S11 illustrates the importance of the pulse number used for performing the LTP/LTD cycles. In this experiment, long pulses were used (500 ms) and therefore 30 pulses were saturating the conductance of the n-PBDF OECT device during LTP with no significant raise in the drain-source current approximately from the cycle number 20. This effect gives rise to non-linear LTP curves, which is not beneficial for the practical application. In these conditions, we considered 10 cycles as the optimal pulse number for LTP and LTD aiming at a linear LTP response. When the V_{gs} pulses are shorter (Figure S4c and f), the LTP curve maintain the linear increase in the current up to 50 cycles at least.

Characterization of the n-PBDF OEETs for handwritten digit recognition using the long-term potentiation/depression

Figure S12. Characterization of the n-PBDF OEETs for handwritten digit recognition using the long-term potentiation/depression (LTP/LTD) behavior in the optimal conditions: V_{gs} (set) = 0.8 V, V_{gs} (set) = -0.1 V, t_{pulse} (set/reset) = 50 ms [50 pulses]/500 ms [10 pulses]. (a) Plot of recognition accuracy with the number of epochs of a deep neural network DNN trained for handwritten digit classification, comparing the accuracy of the n-PBDF OEET device with the ideal case. (b) Loss versus training epochs plot for the different LTP/LTD conditions and their comparison with the ideal case. (c-d) Confusion matrices obtained after training 50 epochs using the features of the n-PBDF OEETs under different conditions (pulse number and pulse width).